

Modeling the relationship between neuronal activity and the BOLD signal: Contributions from astrocyte calcium dynamics

Federico Tesler^{1*}, Marja-Leena Linne² and Alain Destexhe¹

¹Paris-Saclay University, CNRS, Paris-Saclay Institute of Neuroscience (NeuroPSI), 91400 Saclay, France.

²Tampere University, Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology, 33720 Tampere, Finland.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): ftesler@gmail.com;

Abstract

Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) relies on the coupling between neuronal and vascular activity, but the mechanisms behind this coupling are still under discussion. Recent experimental evidence suggests that calcium signaling may play a significant role in neurovascular coupling. However, it is still controversial where this calcium signal is located (in neurons or elsewhere), how it operates and how relevant is its role. In this paper we introduce a biologically plausible model of the neurovascular coupling and we show that calcium signaling in astrocytes can explain main aspects of the dynamics of the coupling. We find that calcium signaling can explain so-far unrelated features such as the linear and non-linear regimes, the negative vascular response (undershoot) and the emergence of a (calcium-driven) Hemodynamic Response Function. These features are reproduced here for the first time by a single model of the detailed neuronal-astrocyte-vascular pathway. Furthermore, we analyze how information is coded and transmitted from the neuronal to the vascular system and we predict that frequency modulation of astrocytic calcium dynamics plays a key role in this process. Finally, our work provides a framework to link neuronal activity to the BOLD signal, and vice-versa, where neuronal activity can be inferred from the BOLD signal. This opens new ways to link known alterations of astrocytic calcium signaling in neurodegenerative diseases (e.g. Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases) with detectable changes in the neurovascular coupling.

Keywords: fMRI, neurovascular coupling, astrocytes, calcium signaling

1 Introduction

Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) has become one of the leading neuroimaging techniques in neuroscience. fMRI methods rely on the coupling between local neuronal activity and cerebral blood flow (CBF) [1, 2]. In normal conditions an increase in neuronal activity is followed by an increase in CBF, which supplies the necessary oxygen and glucose to sustain the cerebral

metabolism, a process known as *functional hyperemia*. In a healthy brain, the increase in oxygen supply overpasses the oxygen demand generating an increase in the local level of blood oxygenation, which is captured by the BOLD (Blood-Oxygen-Level-Dependent) signal [3]. Although the neurovascular coupling has been extensively demonstrated, the mechanisms behind it remain under discussion.

It is currently believed that glutamatergic synapses may play a central role in functional

21 hyperemia [2, 4, 5], inducing an increase of CBF
22 via two main signaling pathways: a direct neuron-
23 vascular pathway and a neuron-astrocyte-vascular
24 pathway [6, 7]. In both pathways, a glutamate-
25 induced increase in intracellular calcium concen-
26 trations (in neurons or astrocytes) triggers the
27 production and release of a variety of vasomodu-
28 lators which generate a dilation of nearby arterioles
29 and an increase in CBF. Among these vasomodu-
30 lators we find potassium (K^+) and hydrogen (H^+)
31 ions, prostaglandins (PGs), epoxyeicosatrienoic
32 acid (EET) and nitric oxide (NO) [2, 7, 8].

33 The relative relevance of these different signal-
34 ing pathways is still under study. In particular,
35 the role of astrocytes in the neurovascular cou-
36 pling has been in the center of a controversy
37 during the last decade. Some early studies sug-
38 gested that astrocytic response was too slow to
39 account for functional hyperemia [9, 10], which
40 raised doubts about the participation of astrocytes
41 in the coupling. However, due to experimental lim-
42 itations, only somatic responses were measured in
43 these early studies. It was later shown that a fast
44 response can be observed in astrocytic processes
45 and end-feet (from where vasodilators are thought
46 to be released) and can be correlated with the
47 initiation of the vascular response [11–13]. Thus,
48 while a slow (or null) response may occur at the
49 soma level, a fast response at astrocytic micro-
50 domains is likely associated with the activation
51 of the vascular response. Although further stud-
52 ies are necessary, the role of astrocytes in the
53 neurovascular coupling is increasingly accepted
54 [14]. The actual mechanism behind neurovascular
55 coupling is likely a combination of direct neuron-
56 vascular and neuron-astrocyte-vascular pathways,
57 with the role and relevance of these pathways
58 depending on the brain region, cell-type and even
59 brain-state [2, 6, 7].

60 Despite the different sources and effects on the
61 vasculature, one feature that the different coupling
62 mechanisms seem to share is that they are usu-
63 ally associated with some type of fast intracellular
64 calcium (Ca^{2+}) activity. The relation between
65 calcium signaling in the brain and the vascular
66 response has started to be further explored in
67 experiments during the last few years. Calcium
68 activity in neuronal-dendrites, neuronal-body and
69 astrocytes has been analyzed in relation with the
70 vascular response [6, 11, 15–17]. Thus, the exper-
71 imental evidence seems to suggest that calcium

72 signaling (in neurons or astrocytes) may play a
73 central role in the information processing and
74 transmission between the neuronal and vascular
75 systems. There is however little understanding on
76 how the processing of information is performed
77 by the calcium signal and how it operates on the
78 formation of the BOLD signal.

79 The goal of this work is to study the func-
80 tion of astrocytic calcium activity in functional
81 hyperemia. To perform our study we introduce
82 and analyze a biologically plausible model of the
83 neurovascular coupling which incorporates recent
84 experimental findings and modelling tools at the
85 three levels of the system (neuronal, astrocytic,
86 vascular). Following experimental evidence we will
87 consider the (calcium-mediated) release of the
88 prostaglandin PGE2 by astrocytes as the principal
89 vasomodulator acting in the coupling [7, 8]. Neu-
90 ronal (and synaptic) activity will be modeled via a
91 recently developed mean-field description of a net-
92 work of Adaptive Exponential(AdEx) integrate-
93 and-fire neurons [18], which allows us to explicitly
94 integrate neuronal adaptation. The vascular sys-
95 tem will be described by a novel formulation that
96 relates arteriole volume to cyclic-AMP concentra-
97 tion, together with the classical Balloon model for
98 the BOLD signal [19, 20].

99 Starting from a relatively detailed description
100 we will focus on fundamental aspects of the fMRI
101 phenomenology (such as main experimental pro-
102 tocols, the Hemodynamic Response Function, the
103 linearity of the coupling, the post-stimulus under-
104 shoot and the effects of neuronal adaptation) and
105 we will analyze the role of the calcium signal in
106 these processes. Previous studies with models of
107 the neuro-astro-vascular interaction exists [21–24],
108 but to the best of our knowledge, this is the first
109 work that accounts for the above experimental
110 observation of fMRI.

111 We show that information transmission by
112 the calcium signal operates mainly via frequency
113 coding with a small contribution of amplitude
114 modulation. We also show that in our model cal-
115 cium signaling is responsible for both linear and
116 non-linear aspects of the neurovascular coupling.
117 In section 3.3 we show that a calcium-driven
118 Hemodynamic Response Function (HRF) can be
119 generated and that it is equivalent to the one
120 observed experimentally. We corroborate this by
121 comparing our results with the canonical HRF and

we reproduce our simulations using the HRF formalism. We also show that the calcium activity is a better predictor of the BOLD response within this context. In section 3.4 we study situations where the BOLD signals can become negative (post-stimulus undershoot), a well-known feature observed in fMRI experiments. We show that an undershoot in the calcium activity can cause an undershoot in the BOLD signal via a decrease in CBF. Finally, in section 3.5 we study the effects of neuronal adaptation on the calcium and BOLD signals. We show that the calcium signal can capture the effects of neuronal adaptation via calcium-spike frequency adaptation and transmit it to the BOLD signal. In particular we show that adaptation may play a major role in the post-stimulus undershoot, which further stresses the usefulness of adopting a mean-field formalism where adaptation is present. We end by showing how information about the incoming and recurrent neuronal activity can be extracted from the BOLD signal in our modeling framework.

The current work is focused on calcium signaling in astrocytes, however the results of our study can be extended to other calcium-driven neurovascular pathways as we will discuss along the paper.

2 The model

The model of the neurovascular coupling that we propose consists in a feedforward system comprising the neuronal activity, the calcium dynamics in astrocytes and the vascular response. A diagram of the model is shown in Fig. 1. Neuronal activity will be described via a mean-field model of a network of AdEx neurons. Calcium dynamics in astrocytes will be described via the traditional Li-Rinzel model with recent improvements by De Pittà et al. (2009) to incorporate IP3 dynamics by glutamate activation [25, 26]. The Li-Rinzel model describes the flux of Ca^{2+} between the cytosolic and the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) of the cell, which is known to be the main source of calcium activity in astrocytes [7, 8]. To describe the communication between astrocytes and the vascular system we will model the production of the prostaglandin PGE2 (via the arachidonic acid (AA) cascade) and the action of this vasomodulator on arteriolar smooth-cells which induces the changes in cerebral blood flow. Finally, the BOLD

signal generation is modeled via the Balloon model [19]. The details of the model are introduced in the following.

Fig. 1 Diagram of the model of neurovascular coupling. We consider a feedforward system that starts at the neuronal level. Glutamate spilled from the synaptic clefts toward the perisynaptic space activates, through metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluRs), the calcium (Ca^{2+}) signaling cascade in astrocytes. The increase in cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels in astrocytes induces the production and release of vasomodulators (prostaglandin, PG) derived from free arachidonic acid, leading to the variations of the arteriole volume.

2.1 Mean-field neuronal model and synaptic release

To model the neuronal activity we will consider a network of adaptive exponential-integrate-and-fire neurons (AdEx) [27]. We will consider a directed network made by 10000 AdEx neurons, with 80% of excitatory and 20% of inhibitory neurons. Neurons in the network are randomly connected with probability $p = 5\%$ and interact via conductance based synapses (see Supp. Inf. Materials and Methods for details). We will focus on the mean activity of the population. The mean-field equations for the AdEx network are given to a first-order by [18]:

$$T \frac{d\nu_{e,i}}{dt} = F_{e,i}(W, \bar{\nu}_e, \nu_i) - \nu_{e,i} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = -\frac{W}{\tau_w} + b\nu_e + a(\mu_V(\bar{\nu}_e, \nu_i, W) - E_L) \quad (2)$$

where $\nu_{e,i}$ is the mean neuronal firing rate of the excitatory and inhibitory population respectively, W is the mean value of the adaptation variable, F is the neuron transfer function (i.e. output firing rate of a neuron when receiving excitatory and inhibitory inputs with mean rates ν_e

and ν_i and with a level of adaptation W), a and b are the sub-threshold and spiking adaptation constants, t_w is the characteristic time of the adaptation variable and T is a characteristic time for neuronal response (we adopt $t_w = 1$ s and $T = 5$ ms). Values for all the parameters are given in Supp. Inf. Table 1. The stimulation of the network is simulated by an (excitatory) external drive ν_{ext} , which represents the input from a nearby neuronal population and so $\bar{\nu}_e = \nu_e + \nu_{ext}$. The network exhibits no spontaneous activity for the parameters used. Derivation of the mean field equations can be found in Ref. [18].

Synaptic glutamate release can be straightforwardly estimated from the mean-field model. Glutamate concentration ($[Glu]$) is proportional to the mean conductance of excitatory synapses (s) obtained from the (conductance-based) mean-field model [18], $s = \nu_e p N_e Q_e \tau_e$, where N_e is the number of excitatory neurons, Q_e is the excitatory quantal conductance (conductance change induced by a single spike) and τ_e is the conductance decay time (see Supp. Inf. for details and Supp. Inf. Table 1 for the corresponding parameter values). Thus, $[Glu] = gs$, where g is a proportionality constant. For a better analysis, we will separate the contribution of the recurrent excitatory synaptic activity from the one of the external excitatory input. Thus, the mean glutamate concentration in the synaptic cleft is given by:

$$[Glu] = (g_r \nu_e + g_{ext} \nu_{ext}) p N_e Q_e \tau_e \quad (3)$$

where $g_{r/ext}$ is the proportionality constant accounting for the contribution to glutamate release of the recurrent and external excitatory synaptic activity respectively.

We notice that the activity of inhibitory neurons may also be involved in the neurovascular coupling, for example via release of nitric oxide which acts as a vasodilator. Nevertheless, it is currently believed that excitatory synaptic activity dominates the overall ATP cost of neural signaling for which it is expected excitatory activity to be a strong driver of vascular response [28, 29]. In addition, our study is focused on the neuronal-astrocyte interaction which is mainly driven by synaptic glutamatergic release. For these reasons we will focus on the role of synaptic release of excitatory neurons.

2.2 Astrocyte calcium dynamics and arachidonic acid cascade

In this section we present the model used to describe the intracellular calcium dynamics and vasomodulator production by astrocytes. In our model we assume that part of the neuronal glutamate released to the synaptic cleft spills toward the perisynaptic space and activates mGluRs in nearby astrocytes, which triggers the astrocytic calcium signaling. We notice at this point that the exact location and path of the calcium signal within the astrocyte in response to neuronal activity is still under discussion, being the signal likely initiated in astrocytic processes and propagates towards the end-feet where vasodilators are released [11, 30] (although, direct initiation at the end-feet could also be possible [13]). In any case, the propagation and/or initiation of the calcium signal within the astrocyte occurs in times much shorter than the initiation of the vascular response, the former being in the order of tens of milliseconds [11, 13] and the latter in the order of seconds. In our model we will assume that the calcium signal starts at the process-level and propagates to the end-feet. As the time of propagation and/or initiation of the calcium signal is negligible compared to the time of initiation of the vascular response we will neglect any delay due to the signal propagation and assume that calcium transients occur simultaneously in the process and in the end-feet. Thus, we will assume that calcium concentration in both compartments can be described by a single variable Ca^{2+} , where we assume that the signal is preserved during the propagation.

To model the glutamate-induced calcium dynamics in the astrocyte we adopt a recent version of the Li-Rinzel model [25] which incorporates a detailed dynamics of Ca^{2+} -dependent production and degradation of cytosolic inositol trisphosphate (IP3) [26, 31]. In this model, the activation of mGluRs induces an increase of intracellular cytosolic IP3 that triggers the release of calcium from the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) towards the cytosol. This generates a transient increase in cytosolic Ca^{2+} which is later reabsorbed by the ER. For details on the model see Refs. [25, 26, 31] and Supp. Inf. Materials and Methods. The Li-Rinzel model equations for the

290 cytosolic calcium concentration and IP3 gating (h)
291 are given by [25]:

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_t C^{2+} &= J_C(Ca^{2+}, h, IP3) + J_L(Ca^{2+}) - J_P(Ca^{2+}) \\ \partial_t h &= \frac{h_\infty(Ca^{2+}, IP3) - h}{\tau_h(Ca^{2+}, IP3)}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

292 where J_C , J_L , and J_P denote the IP3-
293 mediated Ca^{2+} -induced Ca^{2+} -release from the
294 ER (J_C), the Ca^{2+} leak from the ER (J_L), and
295 the Ca^{2+} uptake from the cytosol back to the ER
296 by serca-ER Ca^{2+} /ATPase pumps (J_P) [141].
297 These terms are given by

$$\begin{aligned}J_C &= \Gamma_C m_\infty^3 h^3 (C_T - (1 + \rho_A)Ca^{2+}) \\ m_\infty &= H(IP3, d_1)H(Ca^{2+}, d_5) \\ J_L &= \Gamma_L (C_T - (1 - \rho_A)C) \\ J_P &= O_P H(Ca^{2+}, K_P) \\ h_\infty &= d_2 \frac{IP3 + d_1}{d_2(IP3 + d_1) + (IP3 + d_3)Ca^{2+}} \\ \tau_h &= \frac{1}{O_2} \frac{IP3 + d_3}{d_2(IP3 + d_1) + (IP3 + d_3)Ca^{2+}}\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

298 :
299 where τ_h is the IP3 receptor (IP3R) deactivation
300 time constant and h_∞ is the steady-state
301 probability. Here C_T is the total calcium con-
302 centration at the ER, ρ_A is the ER-to-cytoplasm
303 volume ratio and Γ 's, d 's and O_2 are constants.
304 For a detailed explanation of the parameters see
305 Supp. Inf. and ref. [31]. In future sections we will
306 explore in particular the effect of the deactivation
307 time constant (τ_h) in the calcium response
308 relevant for the neurovascular coupling.

309 The increase of cytosolic Ca^{2+} activates phos-
310 pholipase A2, which induces the production of
311 arachidonic acid (AA) from membrane phospho-
312 lipids. This in turn leads to the production and
313 release of vasomodulators derived from AA, in
314 particular the vasodilator PGE2 [2, 7, 8]. The pro-
315 duction of AA and PGE2 will be modeled via
316 Michaelis-Menten type of equations [21]:

$$\frac{dAA}{dt} = -\frac{AA}{\tau_{AA}} + \frac{O_{AA}Ca^{2+}}{K_{AA} + Ca^{2+}}\quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dPG}{dt} = -\frac{PG}{\tau_{PG}} + \frac{O_{PG}AA}{K_{PG} + AA}\quad (7)$$

317 where τ_{AA} and τ_{PG} are the time constants for
318 AA and PGE2 respectively, K_{PG} and K_{AA} are
319 the Michaelis constants and O_{PG} , O_{cAMP} are the
320 maximum rate of production of AA and PGE2
321 respectively. We note that this model describes
322 a single cell activity. Vascular activation is most
323 likely not carried out by a single astrocyte (or sin-
324 gle astrocyte process) but by the many astrocytes
325 linked with the local vasculature and neuronal
326 population. Nevertheless, it has been seen that
327 *in vivo* the activity of astrocytes tend to be
328 restricted to independent single-cell activity [32–
329 35] (rather than intercellular calcium waves as
330 seen in *in vitro* experiments [36]). Thus, we will
331 adopt this single-cell model as a representative
332 unit of the astrocytes associated with the same
333 neuronal population.

334 Regarding the adoption of PGE2 as the main
335 vasodilator in the coupling, we follow recent stud-
336 ies that suggest that the main part of the vascular
337 dilation generated by astrocytes ($\sim 70\%$) is driven
338 by prostaglandins [7, 37]. The rest of the dila-
339 tion may be generated by other vasodilators such
340 as EET, and both can be acting together in the
341 coupling [8]. For simplicity in this study we have
342 only considered PGE2, but the incorporation of
343 vasodilators such as EETs can be envisioned for
344 future extensions of our model.

345 Regarding the IP3-related calcium response,
346 we notice that a variety of IP3R calcium channel
347 subtypes have been detected in astrocyte fine pro-
348 cesses [38], although the specific subtypes of IP3
349 receptors potentially involved during fast calcium
350 responses is still under discussion. In this work we
351 assume a generic IP3R involved in the IP3-induced
352 calcium dynamics. A detailed analysis of potential
353 IP3R subtypes is out of the scope of this paper.

354 We point out that levels of calcium concentra-
355 tion in our model are intended to be in agreement
356 with typical values observed in experiments, but
357 these concentration can be adjusted without sig-
358 nificant change in the results presented in the
359 paper.

360 Finally, regarding the type of glutamate recep-
361 tors acting in the calcium transient activation,
362 one possible candidate is the mGluR5, although
363 it has been observed that the expression of this
364 mGluR subtype tends to reduce in adult animals
365 [39, 40]. More recently it has been also proposed
366 that the mGluR3 subtype in combination with
367 other Gq-coupled receptors can be acting behind

368 the activity of calcium transients in astrocytes
 369 [41]. As we did for the IP3R, in this paper we
 370 assume a generic mGluR involved in the calcium
 371 signal activation, and a detailed analysis of mGluR
 372 subtypes is out of the scope of this paper.

373 2.3 Vascular response and BOLD 374 signal

375 We will assume that the vascular response
 376 starts at the arteriole level. We assume that
 377 PGE2 released from astrocytes binds to EP4
 378 prostaglandin receptors on smooth cells of arte-
 379 rioles inducing an increase of cyclic adenosine
 380 monophosphate (cAMP) concentration in the
 381 smooth cells. This generates the activation of
 382 protein kinase A and a decrease in the phospho-
 383 rylation of the myosin light chain. Contraction of
 384 arterioles has been proposed to be proportional to
 385 the concentration of phosphorylated myosin [22].
 386 Following this line, we will assume that arte-
 387 riole dilation is proportional to the concentration
 388 of cAMP. The equations describing the fraction of
 389 activated PGE2 receptors and the cAMP produc-
 390 tion in arterioles are:

$$\frac{dR_{PG}}{dt} = -\frac{R_{PG}}{\tau_R} + O_R PG(1 - R_{PG}) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dcAMP}{dt} = -\frac{cAMP}{\tau_{cAMP}} + O_{cAMP} R_{PG} \quad (9)$$

391 where R_{PG} is the portion of activated PGE2
 392 receptors, PG is the concentration of PGE2,
 393 τ_{cAMP} is the relaxation time for cAMP, and
 394 O_R , O_{cAMP} are constants. Normalized relative
 395 arteriole volume is given by:

$$CBV_A = 1 + D_A \frac{(cAMP - cAMP_o)}{K_{VA}^2 + (cAMP - cAMP_o)^2} \quad (10)$$

396 where CBV_A is the normalized change of arte-
 397 riole cerebral blood volume relative to its basal
 398 value, $cAMP_o$ is the basal concentration of cAMP
 399 and D_A , K_{VA} are constants.

The relation between CBV and CBF is usu-
 ally assumed to follow a power law. The value of
 the exponent has been observed to depend on the
 specific brain region and vasculature level [42, 43].
 In our model the relative change in cerebral blood

flow evoked by changes in CBV_A is given by:

$$CBF_{IN} = CBV_A^{\frac{1}{\alpha_A}} \quad (11)$$

where α_A is a constant (a different power α_V is
 used for the venule blood volume CBV_V , see Supp.
 Inf. Materials and Methods).

Finally, to generate the BOLD signal evoked
 by the changes of CBF we will adopt the well-
 known Balloon model [19]. This model describes
 the change in deoxyhemoglobin concentration
 (which originates the BOLD signal) generated by
 an increase in CBF. A rough approximation of the
 BOLD signal obtained from the Balloon model in
 terms of CBF is given by [44]:

$$BOLD \approx k_1(CBF_{IN} - 1) \quad (12)$$

where k_1 is a constant. This approximation pro-
 vides a good intuition of the expected BOLD
 response and is given here for reference, however
 it fails to reproduce some key features such as the
 post-stimulus undershoot related with slow venule
 volume relaxation (analyzed later in the paper).
 For all the simulations presented in this paper we
 use the full Balloon model as presented in the
 Supp. Inf. (Materials and Methods). For details
 on the Balloon model see Refs. [19, 20] and Supp.
 Inf. Materials and Methods.

3 Results

In the following we present the results obtained
 from our model. First we analyze the time courses
 of the main variables in the vascular pathway and
 we reproduce some key experimental results from
 fMRI measurements. In particular, we show that
 our simulations can correctly reproduce the results
 of the two main experimental protocols used in
 BOLD imaging, namely i) event-related protocols
 and ii) block protocols. Then we proceed with the
 study of information coding and transmission in
 our system (3.2); the analysis of the linear cou-
 pling and the Hemodynamic Response Function
 formalism (3.3); the analysis of the undershoot of
 the BOLD signal in the context of the calcium
 pathway (3.4); and the effects of neuronal adapta-
 tion on the calcium signal and the BOLD response
 (3.5).

3.1 Event-related and block protocols

In this section we show how the calcium pathway for neuro-vascular coupling operates and we show that we can correctly reproduce the results from the main experimental protocols used in fMRI, which provides a first validation for our model.

Experimental protocols used for BOLD imaging are usually divided in two groups [1, 45, 46]: i) event-related protocols, where short single stimulus are presented with long inter-stimulus intervals (tens of seconds, equal or larger than typical BOLD response time-course); and ii) block protocols, where multiple stimuli are presented with very short inter-stimulus intervals, followed by a longer 'inter-block' interval after which a new set ('block') of stimuli is presented. In both protocols stimulus duration can be in the order of 4s or less. Variations and mixed-type protocols are also used. For a detailed analysis of the protocols and their advantages see Refs. [1, 45–48]. We notice that these two protocols are related to fundamental features of the neurovascular coupling, which are the vascular response to an impulse stimulus and the response to a superposition of stimulus. The analysis of of these two features constitutes an important part of this work.

The results of our simulations for the two protocols are shown in Fig. 2. Comparison with experimental results are shown in panel (b). Except otherwise indicated, the stimulus used in the paper will consist in a pulse of the external input ν_{ext} as shown in the top panel of Fig.2.a (the width of the pulse corresponds to the duration of the stimulus). The response obtained for a single (short) event is usually known as the Hemodynamic Response Function (HRF) and correspond to the minimum BOLD response in functional hyperemia. The same response is obtained for any stimulus of shorter duration surpassing a certain threshold in time and intensity. In our model, this minimum response corresponds to the activation of a calcium-spike as we will show later. As we see from the figure, our simulations can capture main features of the HRF: i) a lag of $t_{ON} \approx 2$ seconds between the application of the stimulus and the activation of the response; a lag of $t_{peak} \approx 5$ seconds between the application of the stimulus and the peak of the response; a maximum amplitude

Fig. 2 Standard experimental protocols for fMRI measurements. a) Simulations of the event-related and block protocols. The event-related case consists in the application of a single stimulus of 2s. The block-protocol consists in the application of 10 stimuli of 2 seconds each, separated by an inter-stimulus interval of 1 second. b) Experimental results for the two standard protocols. Left: results from an event-related protocol for three different stimulus strength (stimulus duration of 3 seconds), adapted from Ref. [49]. Right: results from a block protocol with 2.5 seconds stimulus and an inter-stimulus interval of 0.5 seconds, adapted from Ref. [48].

that range between 1% and 2% (measured as percentage change from the basal level); a marked post-stimulus undershoot; and a total duration in the order of few tens of seconds. The HRF is analyzed in detail in section 3.3. From the simulation of the block protocol we see that we can correctly capture the response to the superposition of events (further analysis on this is developed in section 3.3).

To provide a better understanding of the mechanism of the BOLD generation in our system we show in Fig. 3 the time course of the main variables of the model for stimuli of two different duration (4s and 24s). In Fig.3 (top panels) we see that a fast neuronal response is generated after the application of the stimulus, which exhibits a marked overshoot given by the strong adaptation effect. This neuronal response generates an increase in the perisynaptic glutamate concentration (second panels from top) that triggers the

481
482
483
484
485
486
487
488
489
490
491
492
493
494
495
496
497
498
499
500

501 activation of the calcium dynamics in the astro-
 502 cyte (characterized by calcium-spikes as seen in
 503 Fig. 3 third panels from top). The Ca^{2+} activ-
 504 ity leads to the increase in cerebral blood flow
 505 (CBF_{IN} , bottom panels) driven by the release of
 506 the vasomodulator PGE2 and the increase in arte-
 507 riolar volume (not shown, see Supp. Inf. Materials
 508 and Methods for the time course of the remain-
 509 ing variables). We notice that CBF_{IN} is linked
 510 to the arteriolar volume CBV_A . Timing and size
 511 differences between arteriolar and venular volume
 512 changes are also correctly captured by our simu-
 513 lations and are shown in the Supp. Inf. Materials
 514 and Methods. As we will see in the next section,
 515 the information about the external stimulus is
 516 coded in terms of the frequency and amplitude of
 517 calcium spikes.

518 In the simulations presented in this section we
 519 set $g_{ext} = 0$ in Eq.3, meaning that the gluta-
 520 mate release is proportional to the local excitatory
 521 activity ν_e . Nevertheless, we notice that, for the
 522 level of neuronal adaptation that we use, the
 523 asymptotic activity of the population is mainly
 524 driven by the external input with a small contri-
 525 bution of the recurrent activity (and ν_e is nearly
 526 proportional to ν_{ext} , as seen in the next section).
 527 The recurrent activity is only relevant during a
 528 short period after the stimulus onset (neuronal
 529 overshoot), defined by the characteristic time of
 530 the adaptation variable (t_w). As this characteris-
 531 tic time is short compared to the calcium response,
 532 then the BOLD response in these simulations is
 533 mainly driven by the asymptotic neuronal activity
 534 (and thus by the external input). Thus, the results
 535 presented here for the BOLD signal are nearly
 536 independent of the $g_{r/ext}$ values we use. We will
 537 use $g_{ext} = 0$ through the paper, except otherwise
 538 indicated. As we will see in section 3.5, when t_w is
 539 comparable to the time of the calcium response,
 540 then the adaptation effects have a relevant impact
 541 in the BOLD response and, in particular, we will
 542 see that information of the recurrent neuronal
 543 activity can be extracted from the post-stimulus
 544 undershoot of the BOLD signal.

545 3.2 Calcium coding and BOLD 546 response

547 In this section we analyze how the information
 548 about the input stimulus and the neuronal activity
 549 is codified and transmitted by the calcium signal

Fig. 3 Time course of main model variables for a stimulus of 4 seconds (left) and 24 seconds (right). The interval of stimulus application is indicated by the grey area. The figure illustrates the calcium pathway of neurovascular coupling in the model. The stimulus (represented as an increase in the external input ν_{ext} , not shown) generates an increase in neuronal activity (top panel) which induces a rise in the level of perisynaptic glutamate concentration (second panel). Glutamate triggers the activation of calcium dynamics in astrocytes which is characterized by brief calcium 'spikes' as seen in the figure (third panels from the top). This leads to the production and release of the vasomodulator PGE2 (not shown, see Supp. Inf. Materials and Methods) which dilates the nearby arteriolar and increases the flow of blood into the tissue (bottom panel). The simulations correspond to $\nu_{ext}=4\text{Hz}$.

550 to the vascular system. In particular, we focus on
 551 how the intensity of the stimulus (represented by
 552 the external input ν_{ext}) is codified. We separate
 553 the coding of the input stimulus into two parts:
 554 the first coding performed by the neuronal activity
 555 and the subsequent coding of the neuronal activ-
 556 ity performed by the calcium signal. In Fig.4.a we
 557 show the response of the excitatory neuronal popu-
 558 lation as a function of the external input ν_{ext} ,
 559 obtained from the mean field model (Eqs. 1 and
 560 2). The curve corresponds to the steady value of
 561 the neuronal activity, after ν_E and W have
 562 reached an equilibrium. The response exhibits a
 563 non-linear behaviour with signs of saturation for
 564 the highest inputs. This neuronal activity is then
 565 sensed by the astrocyte and codified by means of
 566 the intracellular calcium signal. We notice that
 567 the neuronal-astrocyte communication is made
 568 through glutamate release, which in our model
 569 operates linearly on the curve of Fig.4.a. In Fig.4.b
 570 we show the time course of the calcium signal for

571 two different inputs ($\nu_{ext}=3$ and 6 Hz) and in panels (c),(d) we show the evolution of the frequency
 572 (f_{Ca}) and amplitude (A_{Ca}) of the calcium signal as a function of the neuronal (excitatory) firing
 573 rate (ν_E). It can be seen that the neuronal activity is codified by the calcium signal in terms of both
 574 its frequency and amplitude. We observe that the signal exhibits a threshold for calcium-spike gener-
 575 ation, under which no spike is observed. Over the threshold, both amplitude and frequency are
 576 monotonic increasing functions of the firing rate (for a detailed analysis of the calcium dynamics
 577 and the coding modes see Supp. Inf. and Ref.[26]). The modulation of the frequency and amplitude
 578 by the neuronal activity is made via the control of the IP3 production rate by glutamate concentra-
 579 tion as given in the modified Li-Rinzel model (see Ref. [31] and Supp. Inf.).

580 The frequency-input relation of the calcium response can be correctly described by a logarithmic
 581 function. A similar functional description has been proposed before for analogous gating dynam-
 582 ics [50, 51]. We show in Fig.4.d the results of a fit over the $f_{Ca} - \nu_E$ curve with the function
 583 $f(x) = A \ln(\frac{x-x_o}{B})$, where $A = 0.12$, $x_o = 0.58$ and $B = 0.05$. We notice that the expression used for
 584 the fit is purely phenomenological. Nevertheless it provides a quantitative description of the calcium
 585 frequency response that will be of use for later analysis in the paper. We notice in addition that
 586 the maximum value of f_{Ca} is mainly defined by the deinactivation time of the IP3 gated channels
 587 that establishes a refractory time for calcium-spike generation. An analysis of the frequency-range is
 588 given in section 3.6.

589 Finally, the calcium signal is transmitted to and decoded by the vascular system through the
 590 arachidonic acid avalanche and cAMP pathway as explained in the previous sections. In Fig.4.e we
 591 show the BOLD response for three different inputs ($\nu_{ext}=3, 4$ and 6 Hz). We see that the variation
 592 in the input performs basically a re-scale in the amplitude of the BOLD signal.

593 In Fig.4.f we show the amplitude of the BOLD response as a function of the neuronal activity ν_E .
 594 A linear fit is shown in red dashed line, which describes nearly 75% of the total BOLD variation
 595 in our simulations. After this linear regime, a saturation in the response is observed. In Fig.4.g-h
 596 we show the BOLD response to input intensity parameterized in terms of calcium-spike amplitude
 597 and frequency. A similar relation between BOLD

Fig. 4 Neuron and calcium coding of an external stimulus. a) Average firing rate of the excitatory neuronal population as a function of the external stimulus intensity (in terms of the external excitatory rate ν_{ext}). b) Astrocytic calcium activity for two values of ν_{ext} . c-d) Amplitude and frequency of calcium spikes as a function of excitatory firing rate. External stimuli are first codified by neuronal activity which modulates the amplitude and frequency of the calcium response. In panel (d) we show a fit with a logarithmic function (solid blue line, see main-text). e) BOLD response for different stimulus intensity (for a comparison with experimental results see Fig. 2.b). In dashed line we show the results for $\nu_{ext}=6$ Hz with calcium-spike amplitude limited to $A_{Ca}=0.65\mu\text{M}$ for arachidonic acid production, indicating that the main increase in BOLD response is not driven by the spike-amplitude. Frequency-coding accounts for about 95% of the variation. f) BOLD response as a function of excitatory activity. A linear fit is shown in red dashed line, which describes $\sim 75\%$ of the total BOLD variation. g-h) BOLD response to stimuli intensity parameterized in terms of calcium-spike amplitude and frequency. A linear fit is provided in panel (h) (dashed red line). For a comparison of panel (g) with experimental results see Ref.[17].

and frequency. A similar relation between BOLD

and the amplitude of astrocytic Ca^{2+} signal has been seen in experiments [17]. Nevertheless, we notice that the change in BOLD response in our simulations is mainly driven by the frequency of the calcium signal and not by its amplitude. We show this in Fig.4.e (dashed line) by imposing a fixed A_{Ca} for arachidonic acid production. The change in f_{Ca} accounts for more than 95% of the BOLD amplitude variation, while the other less than 5% is given by the change in A_{Ca} . In addition, we see that the BOLD- f_{Ca} relation is approximately linear, except near the threshold where the linearity is lost.

The threshold for calcium-spike generation observed in the model is related with the balance between Ca^{2+} release and re-uptake from the ER of the cell, together with the IP3 activation of calcium channels (see Eq. 4). Given the non-linearity of the system, this threshold has a strong dependency on the maximum rates of glutamate-dependent IP3 production and on the rate of IP3-induced calcium release from endoplasmic reticulum. Dysfunctions in the rate of calcium release (for example, by variation in the density of IP3 receptors in the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum) may lead to an increase in the threshold level of glutamate concentration for calcium-spike activation, meaning that a higher synaptic activity would be necessary to evoke a significant hemodynamic response. Further increase in the threshold level would lead to a decoupling of the neurovascular response (an example of such a dysfunction is presented in the Supp. Inf.).

3.3 Linear coupling and the Hemodynamic Response Function

The BOLD response shown in Fig.2.a for a single short (<4s) stimulus is known as the Hemodynamic Response Function (HRF). In fMRI experiments it is usually assumed that the neuronal and vascular activity are linearly coupled, which has shown to be valid in a certain parameter range [6, 49]. Assuming that the coupling is linear and time invariant, it is possible to write the vascular (BOLD) response as [49]:

$$BOLD = \int HRF(t - \tau)r(s, t) \quad (13)$$

where $r(s, t)$ is the time course of neuronal activity of the local population, being s the intensity of the stimulus or other stimulus parameter under study. In this section we study the HRF obtained from our model and the validity of the linear analysis. The HRF obtained for a stimulus of 2 seconds and $\nu_{ext}=4\text{Hz}$ is shown in detail in Fig.5.a. Main features of the HRF (indicated in the figure) observed in experiments comprise: i) a lag of $t_{ON} \approx 2$ seconds between the application of the stimulus and the activation of the response, ii) a lag of $t_{peak} \approx 5$ seconds between the application of the stimulus and the peak of the response, iii) a maximum amplitude that ranges between 1% and 2% (measured as percentage change from the basal level) and iv) a marked post-stimulus undershoot [47, 49]. As shown in Fig.5.a, all these features are correctly captured by our model. For completeness we show in the figure a fit performed with the so called canonical HRF, a phenomenological expression widely used for fMRI data analysis. As we see the HRF obtained from our model is in good agreement with the canonical HRF.

In Fig.5.b-c we show the BOLD response obtained from the simulations together with the results from Eq.13 (for a pulse and an oscillatory stimuli respectively). As we can see the HRF formalism can correctly reproduce the simulations result within the predicted linear range. Thus, in our model the calcium pathway generates a neurovascular coupling that behaves linearly close to the threshold of BOLD (and calcium) activation ($\nu_{ext} \approx 2.4$) and for a range of more than a twofold change in neuronal activity which accounts for a about 75% of the total change in BOLD signal in our simulations.

Based on the analysis performed so far and the results shown in Fig.4, we propose now to use the calcium activity as a predictor of the BOLD response instead of the neuronal activity. In Fig.4.h we can see that the BOLD follows a linear relation with the calcium firing rate (f_{Ca}), which makes it a good candidate for the HRF formalism. Thus, we will replace the function $r(s, t)$ from Eq.13 by $c(s, t)$, corresponding to the calcium activity. In Fig.5.d-e) we show the results of the convolution between HRF and the time course of the calcium activity. We see that the convolution can correctly reproduce the results of the simulations for barely the entire range, except close

Fig. 5 a) Hemodynamic Response Function (HRF) obtained from our model, corresponding to a stimulus of 2 seconds and $\nu_{ext}=4\text{Hz}$ (blue solid line). A fit with a double-gamma canonical HRF is shown (red dashed line), $\text{HRF}_C = \left(\frac{t}{d_1}\right)^{a_1} e^{-(t-d_1)/b_1} - c\left(\frac{t}{d_2}\right)^{a_2} e^{-(t-d_2)/b_2}$. The coefficients from the fit are $d_1 = 6\text{s}$, $a_1 = 6$, $b_1 = 1\text{s}$, $c = 0.07$, $d_2 = 18\text{s}$, $a_2 = 12$, $b_2 = 1.5\text{s}$, in good agreement with experimental values [52, 53]. In panel (b) and (c) we show the BOLD response together with the result from the convolution of Eq.13. In panel (b) we show the results for a 24 seconds stimulus with $\nu_{ext}=3$ and 4Hz. In panel (c) we show the results for a sinusoidal stimulus centered at $\nu_{ext}=4.2\text{Hz}$ and amplitude of 1.6Hz. We see that the results from the convolution fails to reproduce the simulations for the higher values of the input as the system moves away from the linear regime. In panel (d) and (e) we show the BOLD response estimated via the convolution of the HRF with the calcium activity (for the same stimuli as panels (b)-(c) respectively). From panel (e) we see that the results from the convolution can reproduce the simulations except for the lower values of the input (close the threshold for calcium activation) as the system moves away from the linear regime.

to the threshold where the BOLD- f_{Ca} relation deviates from the linearity.

In this section we have proved that the calcium activity is a good indicator of the BOLD

activity and that it can be incorporated to the linear HRF formalism, exhibiting a range of validity larger than its neuronal counterpart. In addition, the fact that the HRF formalism is compatible with our model (and that our HRF is equivalent to the canonical HRF), indicates that the analysis performed in this paper for the calcium pathway of neurovascular coupling can be generalized to other models. Independently of the exact path that links the calcium activity with the vascular system, we have shown that the calcium-vascular link can be replaced by the linear HRF formalism using a canonical HRF which are experimentally tested and widely accepted. This makes the analysis presented in the following sections extensible to other alternative paths as far the linearity of the calcium-vascular relation remains valid. The linear and non-linear regimes of the coupling in our model depend mainly on the transfer function (frequency response) of the astrocytic calcium dynamics. The origin of the saturation can be traced to both the IP₃ and the pure calcium dynamics from the Li-Rinzel model. In the Li-Rinzel model, the frequency of calcium-spikes is given by the concentration of IP₃ and it exhibits a frequency-lock for sufficiently high concentrations of IP₃ (i.e. the frequency remains unchanged for higher values of IP₃). In addition, the IP₃ dynamics used in our model (which depends on the glutamate concentration) exhibits a saturation in the maximum concentration of IP₃ for sufficiently high values of glutamate. The glutamate and IP₃ concentrations at which saturation appears depend primarily on the maximum rates of glutamate-dependent IP₃ production and on the affinity of IP₃-receptors in the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum that mediate the calcium release. Finally, we notice that, although the HRF is driven by the calcium dynamics (being a single calcium-spike the minimum activation 'unit'), the characteristic times of the HRF (t_{ON} , t_{peak}) depend on the whole dynamics of the system. Thus, even when the calcium-spike frequency changes with the stimulus intensity, these changes have a relative small impact in the characteristic times of the HRF. The fact that the shape of the HRF does not change with the stimulus strength is a fundamental feature for the validity of the HRF formalism (see, for example, time-contrast separability in ref.[49]).

3.4 BOLD undershoot and calcium dynamics

One characteristic feature of the BOLD response is the presence of a post-stimulus undershoot. The origin of this undershoot is usually attributed to three main sources: a) a slow recovery of the venule volume [19, 54]; b) sustained post-stimulus metabolic rate of oxygen [42]; and c) a post-stimulus undershoot in cerebral blood flow (CBF) [54]. The first of this sources is captured by the Balloon model [19] and is thus incorporated in our simulations. In this section we will focus on the third of this sources, namely the post-stimulus undershoot in CBF. The second source is not incorporated in the current version of our model, but it might be object of future analysis.

In our model the level of CBF is modulated by the calcium activity. In Fig.6.a we show the time course of the calcium signal and the CBF_{IN} during the application of a stimulus. We see that after each calcium-spike there is a period where the Ca^{2+} level goes below its basal state. This is generated by the fast decrease of IP₃ levels driven by the calcium-spike (for details see Supp. Inf. Materials and Methods). While the stimulus is applied the IP₃ levels rise again and a new spike is generated. However, in the post-stimulus phase the IP₃ level slowly recovers until it reaches its basal concentration. During this last period the Ca^{2+} level also remains below its basal concentration giving place to a post-stimulus undershoot in the calcium signal.

This undershoot is transmitted to the CBF_{IN} as shown in Fig.6.a (bottom panel). The size and duration of this undershoot depends on the intensity of the stimulus and on the phase of the calcium oscillation. In Fig.6.b we show the relation between the amplitude of the BOLD undershoot and the amplitude of the calcium undershoot (A_{CaU}), measured as the minimum value of the BOLD and calcium signals respectively. We see that the calcium undershoot in our simulations can account for up to 50% change of the BOLD undershoot.

3.5 Adaptation Effects

In this section we analyze the effects of neuronal adaptation in the neurovascular coupling. In our model the adaptation is described within

Fig. 6 Calcium effects in BOLD post-stimulus undershoot. a) Top panel: calcium time course during stimulation. After the stimulus is removed the calcium signal remains below its basal level and slowly recovers (indicated as *Undershoot* in the figure). The depressed calcium level leads to a post-stimulus undershoot in the blood flow (CBF_{IN}) which is shown in the bottom panel. b) Evolution of the BOLD undershoot amplitude as a function of the calcium undershoot amplitude. We see that the changes in the calcium level lead to a variation of 50% in the BOLD undershoot.

the mean-field formulation by the variable W (see Eqs. 1 and 2), which accounts for the average adaptation of the AdEx neuronal population. We focus here only on the spike-triggered adaptation characterized by the parameter b (we use $a=0$ in Eq.2). The action of adaptation in neuronal activity can be seen in the first and second panels (from the top) of Fig.3. At the onset of the stimulus the neuronal activity exhibits a large overshoot generated by the interplay of the fast neuronal response and the slower adaptation variable W . Similarly, an undershoot in the neuronal activity is observed after the end of the stimulus, generated by the same mechanism. This dynamics is also captured by the glutamate concentration, which follows the variations in neuronal activity. If the characteristic time of the neuronal adaptation (given by t_w) is much smaller than the characteristic time of the calcium response, then the adaptation effects become negligible for the neurovascular coupling and no effects are observed in the BOLD signal. This has been the case for the simulations presented in the previous sections, where we adopted $t_w=1s$.

The situation changes as the characteristic time of adaptation becomes comparable to the time of the calcium response. In Fig.7 we show the results for the case $t_w=5s$. In panel (a) we show the neuronal (top) and BOLD responses (bottom) and we compare them with results having no adaptation ($b^*=0$, see caption in Fig. 7).

852 In this case the adaptation effects are clearly
 853 observed in the BOLD signal. At the onset of the
 854 stimulus we observe the larger BOLD response
 855 in the blue curve ($b \neq 0$) driven by the initial
 856 neuronal overshoot. Although the variation
 857 is small, we see that the response is not only
 858 larger but its maximum value is reached earlier
 859 than expected when no adaptation is considered,
 860 which is a feature observed and discussed in exper-
 861 iments [49]. In addition, after the stimulus, we see
 862 a large variation in the amplitude of the under-
 863 shoot on the BOLD signal. These two effects can
 864 be traced to the calcium dynamics shown in panel
 865 (b). Here we can see the effects of the adapta-
 866 tion acting on the frequency and amplitude of the
 867 calcium-spikes at the onset of the stimulus: the
 868 initial increase in glutamate concentration gener-
 869 ated by the neuronal overshoot leads to a higher
 870 calcium frequency and amplitude which quickly
 871 decreases and reaches a lower steady state after a
 872 few seconds. This leads to the larger initial BOLD
 873 response. On the other hand, the post-stimulus
 874 neuronal undershoot generates a decrease in the
 875 post-stimulus calcium concentration which is the
 876 origin of the larger undershoot observed in BOLD
 877 response. In panel (c) we show the variations in the
 878 BOLD undershoot as a function of the adaptation
 879 parameter b . We see that the post-stimulus neu-
 880 ronal undershoot can account for up to 70% of the
 881 BOLD undershoot for the larger values of b (for
 882 the details of the plot see caption). We notice that
 883 this neuronal dynamics also leads to a dependence
 884 of the PSU on the duration and strength of the
 885 stimulus. For short stimulus (compared to the W
 886 response) the influence of neuronal adaptation will
 887 be limited, for which a smaller neuronal-driven
 888 PSU in the BOLD signal is obtained.

889 Finally, we notice that the results presented
 890 so far correspond to the case $g_{ext} = 0$ in Eq.3,
 891 meaning that the only source of glutamate release
 892 is the recurrent synaptic activity (which repre-
 893 sents the output of the local neuronal population).
 894 As we explained in previous sections, when t_w is
 895 small then the results obtained for the BOLD sig-
 896 nal are nearly independent of the choice of $g_{r/ext}$.
 897 However, when t_w is increased and the adapta-
 898 tion effects are captured by the BOLD signal as in
 899 this section, then the relative contribution of the
 900 recurrent and incoming synaptic activity to gluta-
 901 mate release becomes relevant (where we assume

902 that the incoming activity exhibits no adapta- 902
 903 tion). In Fig.7.d we show the results for the case 903
 904 $g_{ext} = g_r$ (i.e. equal contribution). We show in 904
 905 the figure the time course of the glutamate con- 905
 906 centration (right panel), where we can see that 906
 907 the effects of the neuronal adaptation are drasti- 907
 908 cally reduced in comparison to the case with 908
 909 $g_{ext} = 0$. Furthermore, we can see that there is 909
 910 no observable variation in the BOLD signal (left 910
 911 panel) for the simulations with or without adapta- 911
 912 tion. In particular, the post-stimulus undershoot 912
 913 in the BOLD signal is no longer influenced by 913
 914 the neuronal adaptation. This indicates that the 914
 915 amplitude of the PSU depends on the relative 915
 916 size of the input and output (recurrent activity) 916
 917 of the local neuronal population. Thus, one possi- 917
 918 ble interpretation is that the amplitude of the 918
 919 BOLD signal provides information mainly about 919
 920 the input to the neuronal population, while the 920
 921 amplitude of the PSU provides information about 921
 922 its output. 922
 923

924 3.6 Model robustness and further 924 925 comparison with experimental 925 926 results 926

927 In this section we analyze some important aspects 927
 928 related to the robustness of our model and we per- 928
 929 form further comparison between our simulations 929
 930 and experimental results. 930

931 Among the different components of the model 931
 932 presented in this paper, one of the main novelties 932
 933 is the inclusion of the detailed astrocytic calcium 933
 934 dynamics as a key element to explain main aspects 934
 935 of the neurovascular coupling. In particular we 935
 936 have seen that the frequency-input relationship 936
 937 emerging from the modified Li-Rinzel model for 937
 938 Ca^{2+} plays a key role in the communication between 938
 939 the neuronal and vascular systems. Although a 939
 940 detailed analysis of the Li-Rinzel model has been 940
 941 performed before [26] (and is out of the scope of 941
 942 this paper), it is important to mention a few 942
 943 aspects that are relevant to our current study. We 943
 944 start by noticing that in the Li-Rinzel model Ca- 944
 945 spikes are triggered via IP3 gated channels (see 945
 946 Eqs. 4 and 5). The deinactivation time of these 946
 947 channels gives place to a 'refractory-period' for 947
 948 Ca-spikes which determines the maximum spiking 948
 949 frequency. Thus, the frequency range of calcium 949

Fig. 7 Neuronal adaptation effects in BOLD signal. a) Top: neuronal activity during stimulus application with (green) and without (orange) adaptation (for a better comparison, we re-scale the asymptotic firing rate for $b = 0$ to match the one of $b = 60\text{pA}$, so we indicate it with b^*). Bottom: BOLD response with (blue) and without (orange) adaptation. The effects of adaptation can be observed in the higher initial response for the blue curve and in the larger post-stimulus undershoot. The simulations correspond to $t_w = 5\text{s}$. b) Calcium-spike adaptation. The frequency and amplitude of the calcium-spikes are modulated by the changes of glutamate concentration due to neuronal adaptation. In the figure we can see the adaptation effects occurring during the first three calcium-spikes after which a steady state is reached. In addition, a decrease in the post-stimulus calcium concentration is induced by the neuronal post-stimulus undershoot. The calcium time course shown correspond to the lapse within the red circles indicated in top panel (a). c) Adaptation effects in the post-stimulus undershoot (PSU) of the BOLD response. The plot shows the variation in the PSU of the BOLD response as a function of the adaptation constant b (see Eq. 2). The variations in the undershoot are measured as $\Delta U/U = (\min(\text{BOLD}) - \min(\text{BOLD}_{Ad})) / \min(\text{BOLD})$, where $\min()$ indicates the minimum value and BOLD_{Ad} correspond to the BOLD response when neuronal post-stimulus undershoot is removed. In our simulations the undershoot of the neuronal activity is responsible of up to about 70% of the neuronal PSU for the highest values of b (with $t_w = 5\text{s}$). d) Simulation results for $g_r = g_{ext}$ (equal contribution of external and recurrent activity to glutamate release). We show the BOLD response (left) and glutamate concentration (right). In this case the effects of neuronal adaptation on the BOLD signal are neglectable. The comparison with previous panels ($g_{ext} = 0$), indicates that information about relative role of recurrent activity can be extracted from the post-stimulus undershoot.

spikes can in principle be modulated by the deactivation time. In Fig. 8.a we show the results of the frequency-input curve for different values of the parameters from Eq. 5. In the figure, the frequency range is doubled from the original, still holding the same functional dependence (a fit with a logarithmic function is shown for each case). Although we have adapted for our main study a set of parameters previously used in the literature [26, 31], this shows that the analysis performed here remains valid for larger ranges on the frequency-input relation, which may also lead to a larger range in the BOLD response.

A second important aspect of the calcium dynamics is its response time after the application of the stimulus. It has been experimentally observed that a typical interval of approximately 1 s occurs between the astrocyte and CBF activation [55], while another interval of approximately 1 s is expected between the neuronal and astrocytic responses [24]. The sum of these two intervals constitutes the total neuronal-to-CBF response time, which is captured in the HRF shown in previous sections. In our model, the response time of the astrocyte depends in principle on the strength of the stimulus and is not a constant, as shown in Fig. 8.b. Nevertheless, we notice that this time converges quickly to a stationary value near 1 s, while it rapidly increases as it gets close to the threshold for astrocytic Ca^{2+} activation. This type of non-linearities are actually expected in vascular responses for short or low amplitude stimuli [56]. The quick convergence of the activation time is of great relevance for the validity of the HRF analysis, as it guaranties the invariance of the HRF.

To provide a better quantitative comparison between our model and actual experimental results, we analyze now the dependence of the amplitude of the BOLD signal on the strength of the stimulus. It has been shown in fMRI experiments that the amplitude of the BOLD signal can be described by the expression $f(x) = \frac{ax^p}{x^p + b}$, where x is the input strength (contrast) and a, p, b are constants [49]. In Fig. 8.c we show the results of the fit of our simulations with this expression. We obtain $p = 1.08$ which is in agreement with the experimental results [49] ($a = 3.69$ and $b = 0.95$ are parameters that depend on the particular range of the stimulus and amplitude). This provides further validation to the BOLD signal

950
951
952
953
954
955
956
957
958
959
960
961
962
963
964
965
966
967
968
969
970
971
972
973
974
975
976
977
978
979
980
981
982
983
984
985
986
987
988
989
990
991
992
993
994
995
996
997
998
999
1000

1001 obtained from our model. In addition we show in
 1002 Fig. 8.d the evolution of the onset time t_{ON} of
 1003 the BOLD response as a function of the stimuli.
 1004 In agreement with the calcium response discussed
 1005 before, it experiences a non-linearity close to the
 1006 threshold for the response activation and converges
 1007 rapidly to a stationary value of ~ 2.5 s
 1008 in agreement with experimental results. As men-
 1009 tioned before, this non-linearity is also observed
 1010 in experimental measurements for short or low
 1011 amplitude stimuli [56].

1012 Finally, for completeness we show in Fig. 8.e
 1013 the evolution of the vasculature volume and blood
 1014 flow under the presentation of a stimulus. We
 1015 show here the normalized variation of the vol-
 1016 ume at the arteriole and venule level, together
 1017 with the incoming and outgoing blood flow. The
 1018 amplitudes obtained for the different variables are
 1019 in agreement with typical experimental results
 1020 obtained via MRI and arterial spin labelling mea-
 1021 surements [57, 58]. In our simulations arterioles
 1022 experience variations in volume (CBV_A) during
 1023 functional hyperemia with changes from 20% to
 1024 more than 60%, while changes in venules volumes
 1025 (CBV_V) can go up to 20%. Similarly, relative
 1026 changes in cerebral blood flow (CBF) can reach
 1027 more than 70% and are related with the CBV via
 1028 Eq. 11.

1029 Discussion

1030 In this paper we have presented a new frame-
 1031 work for modeling the neurovascular coupling.
 1032 This framework is centered on calcium activity
 1033 in astrocytes, that acts to link the neuronal
 1034 activity to the vascular system. Starting from
 1035 a relatively detailed description of the neuron-
 1036 astrocyte-vascular system, we have focused on
 1037 fundamental aspects of the fMRI phenomenol-
 1038 ogy such as the different experimental designs,
 1039 the Hemodynamic Response Function (HRF), the
 1040 linearity in the coupling, the post-stimulus un-
 1041 der-shoot and the effects of neuronal adaptation. We
 1042 have shown that calcium signaling in astrocytes
 1043 may play a relevant role in all of these fea-
 1044 tures. Previous papers with models of the neuron-
 1045 astrocyte-vascular interaction have been proposed
 1046 [21–24]. Some of these models proposed a phe-
 1047 nomenological approach to describe the role of
 1048 astrocytes [24] or studied limited aspects of the
 1049 neurovascular coupling [21–23]. To the best of our

Fig. 8 a) Calcium spike frequency as a function of the external neuronal (excitatory) firing rate. We show the results for two different set of parameters. In red, the same parameters used for the rest of the paper. In green, parameters leading to a shorter calcium refractory period and higher maximum frequency rate. These results correspond to $O_2 = 0.2 \times 10^3$ (mMs)⁻¹ (red) and $O_2 = 0.2 \times 10^4$ (mMs)⁻¹ (green) in Eq. 5. The rest of the parameters remain unchanged (see Tables 1 and 2 in the Supp. Inf.). We see that the rate increases by a factor larger than two between the two set of parameters. For both cases we show a fit with a logarithmic function (solid blue line), as explained in Section 3.2. b) Calcium response onset time (t_{ON}^{Ca}) as a function of external excitatory firing rate. We see that the time increases rapidly near the threshold for calcium activation, but then it quickly converges to a value close to 1 s. c) Amplitude of the BOLD response as a function of the external excitatory rate (red). We show a fit on the response with a phenomenological expression used in experimental results [49] (solid blue line, see main-text). d) Onset time of the BOLD response. In agreement with panel (b) we see that the time increases rapidly close the threshold for calcium activation and then it quickly converges to a value close to 2 s. e) Dynamics of the vascular response during external stimulation. We show the normalized variable change (Norm. Var. Change) of the Cerebral Blood Volume at the arteriole (CBV_A) and venule level (CBV_V), together with the incoming and outgoing blood flow (CBF_{IN} , CBF_{OUT}).

knowledge, the present work is the first one that 1050

1051 accounts for the above experimental observations
1052 on fMRI.

1053 We have shown that the calcium-driven HRF
1054 generated by our model is equivalent to the one
1055 observed experimentally and we provided a com-
1056 parison with the canonical HRF.

1057 We have seen that calcium signaling can
1058 explain the linear and non-linear features of the
1059 neurovascular coupling. The non-linear features
1060 involve the existence of a threshold of neuronal
1061 activity for vascular activation and saturation
1062 in the BOLD signal for sufficiently high neu-
1063 ronal activity. In parallel our simulations predict
1064 a dynamical range where the coupling is linear.
1065 The linear coupling comprises around 75% of the
1066 total variation in the BOLD signal explored in our
1067 simulations and corresponds to the typical range
1068 of values seen in experiments (variations in the
1069 BOLD signal between 1 and 3 %). We have shown
1070 that within this range we can reproduce our sim-
1071 ulations with the HRF linear formalism, which
1072 is widely used for data-analysis of fMRI exper-
1073 iments. In addition our model predicts that the
1074 BOLD signal is linearly coupled with the calcium
1075 activity, for which we have tested the HRF formal-
1076 ism with the calcium activity (instead of neuronal)
1077 which provides better results.

1078 The way that calcium signal codifies and trans-
1079 mits information from the neuronal to the vascular
1080 system was studied. We have found that, in our
1081 model, the coding is performed mainly via fre-
1082 quency modulation of calcium-spikes with a small
1083 contribution of amplitude modulation (see Supp.
1084 Inf. for a discussion of the BOLD response to
1085 neuronal activity at different frequencies).

1086 Other important aspect studied in the paper
1087 is the role of calcium signal on the BOLD post-
1088 stimulus undershoot (PSU). We have explored the
1089 contributions of neuronal and calcium activity to
1090 the PSU. We have shown that an undershoot in
1091 calcium concentration, which emerges from the
1092 same calcium dynamics, has a relevant contribu-
1093 tion to the PSU. The recovery of the basal calcium
1094 concentration occurs faster than the the recovery
1095 of the BOLD PSU, which indicates that calcium
1096 might have a stronger contribution on the early
1097 phase and on the amplitude of the PSU. Such a
1098 calcium undershoot can be observed experimen-
1099 tally [16, 59–62] and recently its effect on the
1100 arteriole tone has been described [63], but, to the
1101 best of our knowledge, has not been studied so far

1102 in relation to functional hyperemia and the BOLD
1103 signal.

1104 In addition, we have shown that the inclusion
1105 of neuronal adaptation generates a post-stimulus
1106 undershoot in the neuronal activity which is cap-
1107 tured by the calcium signal (coded in terms of
1108 calcium-spike frequency and amplitude adapta-
1109 tion) and transmitted to the vascular PSU. The
1110 contributions of PSU described here operate on
1111 the BOLD via the CBF, i.e. they lead to an
1112 undershoot in the CBF that is then captured
1113 by the BOLD. The existence of such neuronal-
1114 CBF-BOLD undershoot can also be observed in
1115 experimental work [54, 64]. We note that the
1116 undershoot of neuronal activity is independent of
1117 the astrocyte-calcium pathway and its impact on
1118 the BOLD might be taken into account for direct
1119 neuron-vascular interaction. Furthermore, it is
1120 believed that the direct neuron-vascular pathway
1121 also involves calcium activity as a mediator [6, 8],
1122 for which the results obtained from our model
1123 might be generalized for alternative neurovascular
1124 pathways. The impact of neuronal adaptation on
1125 BOLD signal has proven to be of importance in
1126 fMRI experiments and it has led to the develop-
1127 ment of fMRI-adaptation, a technique that makes
1128 use of neuronal adaptation and neuronal speci-
1129 ficity. In this context the adoption of the AdEx
1130 formalism constitutes an important step towards
1131 an accurate description of adaptation effects in the
1132 neurovascular coupling, representing a relevant
1133 improvement with respect to standard neuronal-
1134 mass and field models used for fMRI analysis
1135 [65].

1136 As mentioned in the introduction to this paper,
1137 there is still a debate around the role of astro-
1138 cytes in neurovascular coupling. In this work we
1139 have provided a complete new analysis on how
1140 astrocytes can be acting in the coupling. Further-
1141 more, we have provided a series of results linking
1142 calcium dynamics to the BOLD signal that can
1143 be experimentally studied and tested (such as
1144 the frequency-coding mode, the linearity of this
1145 response, the role of calcium in the post-stimulus
1146 undershoot, etc.). We hope that our work can
1147 contribute to this debate and provide tools for
1148 future experimental analysis to elucidate this very
1149 relevant issue.

1150 Possible extensions of our study may involve
1151 the description of BOLD imaging to a larger scale

(multiple voxels or brain regions) and the analysis of resting state fMRI. There is evidence that astrocytes may also mediate vasoconstriction, which may depend on the metabolic state of cerebral tissue [30]. The role of astrocytes in vasoconstriction can also be incorporated in our model. Indeed, in the current version of the model astrocytes contribute to the basal tone of blood vessels via the maintenance of *cAMP* levels in smooth cells. In the Supp. Inf. we show how astrocyte-mediated vasoconstriction can be incorporated to our model and its potential role in vascular homeostasis. In addition, it has been recently suggested that astrocytes may play a key role in the amplification of functional hyperemia to sustained stimulation, which could be also be part of future studies within our model [66]. On the other hand, inhibitory neurons may also be involved in Functional Hyperemia [29], for example via the release of nitric oxide (which is a known vasodilator) or even via interaction with astrocytic end-feet as has recently been suggested [13]. All these represent interesting paths for future elaborations of our model. The development of realistic models of the neurovascular coupling is currently of great relevance for the analysis of clinical data [14, 67]. Furthermore, the mean-field formalism adopted here provides tools to estimate multiple brain signals such as LFP and MEG [68]. This will give the chance to analyze multimodal experiments, where BOLD imaging is combined with electrical measurements, which is a topic of great interest [14]. Furthermore, our framework can be combined with different neuronal models and has the potential of being incorporated in whole brain simulators such as The Virtual Brain [44, 69].

In addition, since astrocytes play a role in several neurodegenerative diseases [70–72], our modelling framework may be investigated to predict how astrocytic dysfunction in brain disorders can result in detectable changes in neurovascular coupling and BOLD signal. For example, mutations in the *PLA2G6* gene, associated to Parkinson’s disease [73], can lead to a disrupt in the release of Arachidonic Acid from membrane phospholipids and a reduction in calcium responses [72, 74], which could be captured by our model (see Supp. Inf. for an example of astrocytic dysfunction).

Finally, our model may be used for inferring neuronal activity from the BOLD signal,

by reversing the equations (see Supp. Inf. for an example). In principle, this could yield to estimates of the global glutamatergic activity, and thus estimates of the population activity of excitatory neurons. Such estimates should be compared to simultaneous measurements of population activity and BOLD signal. As BOLD-fMRI is one of the leading non-invasive research tools in neuroscience, finding new and better methods to infer neuronal or calcium activity constitutes a promising direction for future work. Such methods can be of great relevance for studies of human brain networks in health and disease.

Acknowledgments

Research supported by the CNRS and the European Union (Human Brain Project H2020-785907, H2020-945539). We thank Noora Pihlajarinne for her assistance with the schematic illustration of the model.

Data Availability

The code used to generate the data analysed during the current study is available in the Zenodo repository, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7801673>.

References

- [1] Huettel, S. A., Song, A. W., McCarthy, G. *et al. Functional magnetic resonance imaging* Vol. 1 (Sinauer Associates Sunderland, MA, 2004).
- [2] Iadecola, C. Neurovascular regulation in the normal brain and in alzheimer’s disease. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* **5** (5), 347–360 (2004) .
- [3] Ogawa, S., Lee, T.-M., Kay, A. R. & Tank, D. W. Brain magnetic resonance imaging with contrast dependent on blood oxygenation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **87** (24), 9868–9872 (1990) .
- [4] Logothetis, N. K., Pauls, J., Augath, M., Trinath, T. & Oeltermann, A. Neurophysiological investigation of the basis of the fmri signal. *Nature* **412** (6843), 150–157 (2001) .

- 1244 [5] Magri, C., Schridde, U., Murayama, Y., Panz- 1286
 1245 eri, S. & Logothetis, N. K. The amplitude and 1287
 1246 timing of the bold signal reflects the relation- 1288
 1247 ship between local field potential power at 1289
 1248 different frequencies. *Journal of Neuroscience* 1290
 1249 **32** (4), 1395–1407 (2012) .
- 1250 [6] Lauritzen, M. Reading vascular changes in 1291
 1251 brain imaging: is dendritic calcium the key? 1292
 1252 *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* **6** (1), 77–85 1293
 1253 (2005) .
- 1254 [7] Attwell, D. *et al.* Glial and neuronal control of 1294
 1255 brain blood flow. *Nature* **468** (7321), 232–243 1295
 1256 (2010) .
- 1257 [8] MacVicar, B. A. & Newman, E. A. Astrocyte 1296
 1258 regulation of blood flow in the brain. *Cold* 1297
 1259 *Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* **7** (5), 1298
 1260 a020388 (2015) .
- 1261 [9] Schulz, K. *et al.* Simultaneous bold fmri and 1299
 1262 fiber-optic calcium recording in rat neocor- 1300
 1263 tex. *Nature Methods* **9** (6), 597–602 (2012) 1301
 1264 .
- 1265 [10] Nizar, K. *et al.* In vivo stimulus-induced 1302
 1266 vasodilation occurs without ip3 receptor acti- 1303
 1267 vation and may precede astrocytic calcium 1304
 1268 increase. *Journal of Neuroscience* **33** (19), 1305
 1269 8411–8422 (2013) .
- 1270 [11] Otsu, Y. *et al.* Calcium dynamics in astro- 1306
 1271 cyte processes during neurovascular coupling. 1307
 1272 *Nature Neuroscience* **18** (2), 210–218 (2015) . 1308
- 1273 [12] Lind, B. L., Brazhe, A. R., Jessen, S. B., Tan, 1309
 1274 F. C. & Lauritzen, M. J. Rapid stimulus- 1310
 1275 evoked astrocyte ca²⁺ elevations and hemo- 1311
 1276 dynamic responses in mouse somatosensory 1312
 1277 cortex in vivo. *Proceedings of the National* 1313
 1278 *Academy of Sciences* **110** (48), E4678–E4687 1314
 1279 (2013) .
- 1280 [13] Lind, B. L. *et al.* Fast ca²⁺ responses 1315
 1281 in astrocyte end-feet and neurovascular cou- 1316
 1282 pling in mice. *Glia* **66** (2), 348–358 (2018) 1317
 1283 .
- 1284 [14] Friston, K. J. *et al.* Dynamic causal modelling 1318
 1285 revisited. *Neuroimage* **199**, 730–744 (2019) . 1319
- [15] He, Y. *et al.* Ultra-slow single-vessel bold 1320
 and cbv-based fmri spatiotemporal dynamics 1321
 and their correlation with neuronal intracel- 1322
 lular calcium signals. *Neuron* **97** (4), 925–939 1323
 (2018) . 1324
- [16] Hillman, E. M. Optical brain imaging in vivo: 1325
 techniques and applications from animal to 1326
 man. *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **12** (5), 1327
 051402 (2007) . 1328
- [17] Wang, M., He, Y., Sejnowski, T. J. & Yu, X. 1329
 Brain-state dependent astrocytic ca²⁺ sig- 1330
 nals are coupled to both positive and negative 1331
 bold-fmri signals. *Proceedings of the National* 1332
Academy of Sciences **115** (7), E1647–E1656 1333
 (2018) . 1334
- [18] Di Volo, M., Romagnoni, A., Capone, C. 1335
 & Destexhe, A. Biologically realistic mean- 1336
 field models of conductance-based networks 1337
 of spiking neurons with adaptation. *Neural* 1338
Computation **31** (4), 653–680 (2019) . 1339
- [19] Buxton, R. B., Wong, E. C. & Frank, L. R. 1340
 Dynamics of blood flow and oxygenation 1341
 changes during brain activation: the balloon 1342
 model. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* 1343
39 (6), 855–864 (1998) . 1344
- [20] Buxton, R. B., Uludağ, K., Dubowitz, D. J. 1345
 & Liu, T. T. Modeling the hemodynamic 1346
 response to brain activation. *Neuroimage* **23**, 1347
 S220–S233 (2004) . 1348
- [21] Hadfield, J., Plank, M. J. & David, T. Mod- 1349
 eling secondary messenger pathways in neu- 1350
 rovascular coupling. *Bulletin of Mathematical* 1351
Biology **75** (3), 428–443 (2013) . 1352
- [22] Bennett, M., Farnell, L. & Gibson, W. Ori- 1353
 gins of blood volume change due to gluta- 1354
 matergic synaptic activity at astrocytes abut- 1355
 ting on arteriolar smooth muscle cells. *Journal* 1356
of Theoretical Biology **250** (1), 172–185 1357
 (2008) . 1358
- [23] Farr, H. & David, T. Models of neurovascu- 1359
 lar coupling via potassium and eet signalling. 1360
Journal of Theoretical Biology **286**, 13–23 1361
 (2011) . 1362

- [24] Pang, J. C., Robinson, P. A., Aquino, K. M. & Vasan, N. Effects of astrocytic dynamics on spatiotemporal hemodynamics: Modeling and enhanced data analysis. *Neuroimage* **147**, 994–1005 (2017) .
- [25] Li, Y.-X. & Rinzel, J. Equations for insp3 receptor-mediated [ca2+] i oscillations derived from a detailed kinetic model: a hodgkin-huxley like formalism. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* **166** (4), 461–473 (1994) .
- [26] De Pittà, M., Goldberg, M., Volman, V., Berry, H. & Ben-Jacob, E. Glutamate regulation of calcium and ip 3 oscillating and pulsating dynamics in astrocytes. *Journal of Biological Physics* **35** (4), 383–411 (2009) .
- [27] Brette, R. & Gerstner, W. Adaptive exponential integrate-and-fire model as an effective description of neuronal activity. *Journal of Neurophysiology* **94** (5), 3637–3642 (2005) .
- [28] Bonvento, G., Sibson, N. & Pellerin, L. Does glutamate image your thoughts? *Trends in Neurosciences* **25** (7), 359–364 (2002) .
- [29] Buxton, R. B. The thermodynamics of thinking: connections between neural activity, energy metabolism and blood flow. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* **376** (1815), 20190624 (2021) .
- [30] Carmignoto, G. & Gómez-Gonzalo, M. The contribution of astrocyte signalling to neurovascular coupling. *Brain Research Reviews* **63** (1-2), 138–148 (2010) .
- [31] De Pittà, M. & Brunel, N. Modulation of synaptic plasticity by glutamatergic gliotransmission: A modeling study. *Neural Plasticity* **2016** (2016) .
- [32] Wang, X. *et al.* Astrocytic ca 2+ signaling evoked by sensory stimulation in vivo. *Nature Neuroscience* **9** (6), 816–823 (2006) .
- [33] Schummers, J., Yu, H. & Sur, M. Tuned responses of astrocytes and their influence on hemodynamic signals in the visual cortex. *Science* **320** (5883), 1638–1643 (2008) .
- [34] Halassa, M. M., Fellin, T., Takano, H., Dong, J.-H. & Haydon, P. G. Synaptic islands defined by the territory of a single astrocyte. *Journal of Neuroscience* **27** (24), 6473–6477 (2007) .
- [35] Breithausen, B., Kautzmann, S., Boehlen, A., Steinhäuser, C. & Henneberger, C. Limited contribution of astroglial gap junction coupling to buffering of extracellular k+ in ca1 stratum radiatum. *Glia* **68** (5), 918–931 (2020) .
- [36] Guthrie, P. B. *et al.* Atp released from astrocytes mediates glial calcium waves. *Journal of Neuroscience* **19** (2), 520–528 (1999) .
- [37] Howarth, C. *et al.* A critical role for astrocytes in hypercapnic vasodilation in brain. *Journal of Neuroscience* **37** (9), 2403–2414 (2017) .
- [38] Sherwood, M. W. *et al.* Astrocytic ip3rs: Contribution to ca2+ signalling and hippocampal ltp. *Glia* **65** (3), 502–513 (2017) .
- [39] Cai, Z., Schools, G. P. & Kimelberg, H. K. Metabotropic glutamate receptors in acutely isolated hippocampal astrocytes: developmental changes of mglur5 mrna and functional expression. *Glia* **29** (1), 70–80 (2000) .
- [40] Panatier, A. & Robitaille, R. Astrocytic mglur5 and the tripartite synapse. *Neuroscience* **323**, 29–34 (2016) .
- [41] Kellner, V. *et al.* Dual metabotropic glutamate receptor signaling enables coordination of astrocyte and neuron activity in developing sensory domains. *Neuron* **109** (16), 2545–2555 (2021) .
- [42] van Zijl, P. C., Hua, J. & Lu, H. The bold post-stimulus undershoot, one of the most debated issues in fmri. *Neuroimage* **62** (2), 1092–1102 (2012) .
- [43] Jin, T. & Kim, S.-G. Cortical layer-dependent dynamic blood oxygenation, cerebral blood flow and cerebral blood volume

- 1414 responses during visual stimulation. *Neuro-* 1454
1415 *image* **43** (1), 1–9 (2008) . 1455
- 1416 [44] Sanz-Leon, P., Knock, S. A., Spiegler, A. & 1456
1417 Jirsa, V. K. Mathematical framework for 1457
1418 large-scale brain network modeling in the virtual 1458
1419 brain. *Neuroimage* **111**, 385–430 (2015) 1459
1420 . 1460
- 1421 [45] Amaro Jr, E. & Barker, G. J. Study design 1461
1422 in fmri: basic principles. *Brain and Cognition* 1462
1423 **60** (3), 220–232 (2006) . 1463
- 1424 [46] Glover, G. H. Overview of functional mag- 1464
1425 netic resonance imaging. *Neurosurgery Clin-* 1465
1426 *ics* **22** (2), 133–139 (2011) . 1466
- 1427 [47] Miezin, F. M., Maccotta, L., Ollinger, J., 1467
1428 Petersen, S. & Buckner, R. Characterizing 1468
1429 the hemodynamic response: effects of pre- 1469
1430 sentation rate, sampling procedure, and the 1470
1431 possibility of ordering brain activity based on 1471
1432 relative timing. *Neuroimage* **11** (6), 735–759 1472
1433 (2000) .
- 1434 [48] Chee, M. W., Venkatraman, V., Westphal, 1473
1435 C. & Siong, S. C. Comparison of block 1474
1436 and event-related fmri designs in evaluat- 1475
1437 ing the word-frequency effect. *Human Brain* 1476
1438 *Mapping* **18** (3), 186–193 (2003) . 1477
- 1439 [49] Boynton, G. M., Engel, S. A., Glover, G. H. 1478
1440 & Heeger, D. J. Linear systems analysis 1479
1441 of functional magnetic resonance imaging in 1480
1442 human v1. *Journal of Neuroscience* **16** (13), 1481
1443 4207–4221 (1996) . 1482
- 1444 [50] Agin, D. Hodgkin-huxley equations: loga- 1483
1445 rithmic relation between membrane current 1484
1446 and frequency of repetitive activity. *Nature* 1485
1447 **201** (4919), 625–626 (1964) . 1486
- 1448 [51] Wang, X.-J. Calcium coding and adaptive 1487
1449 temporal computation in cortical pyramidal 1488
1450 neurons. *Journal of Neurophysiology* (1998) . 1489
- 1451 [52] Worsley, K. J. *et al.* A general statistical anal- 1490
1452 ysis for fmri data. *Neuroimage* **15** (1), 1–15 1491
1453 (2002) .
- [53] Proulx, S. *et al.* Increased sensitivity of fast 1492
bold fmri with a subject-specific hemody- 1493
namic response function and application to 1494
epilepsy. *NeuroImage* **93**, 59–73 (2014) . 1495
- [54] Chen, J. J. & Pike, G. B. Origins of the 1496
bold post-stimulus undershoot. *Neuroimage* 1497
46 (3), 559–568 (2009) .
- [55] Masamoto, K. *et al.* Unveiling astrocytic con- 1498
trol of cerebral blood flow with optogenetics. 1499
Scientific reports **5** (1), 1–11 (2015) . 1500
- [56] Vazquez, A. L. & Noll, D. C. Nonlinear 1501
aspects of the bold response in functional mri. 1502
Neuroimage **7** (2), 108–118 (1998) . 1503
- [57] Kim, T., Hendrich, K. S., Masamoto, K. & 1504
Kim, S.-G. Arterial versus total blood vol- 1505
ume changes during neural activity-induced 1506
cerebral blood flow change: implication for 1507
bold fmri. *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow &* 1508
Metabolism **27** (6), 1235–1247 (2007) . 1509
- [58] Lee, S.-P., Duong, T. Q., Yang, G., Iadecola, 1510
C. & Kim, S.-G. Relative changes of cere- 1511
bral arterial and venous blood volumes dur- 1512
ing increased cerebral blood flow: implica- 1513
tions for bold fmri. *Magnetic Resonance in* 1514
Medicine: An Official Journal of the Inter- 1515
national Society for Magnetic Resonance in 1516
Medicine **45** (5), 791–800 (2001) . 1517
- [59] Bouchard, M. B., Chen, B. R., Burgess, S. A. 1518
& Hillman, E. M. Ultra-fast multispec- 1519
tral optical imaging of cortical oxygenation, 1520
blood flow, and intracellular calcium dynam- 1521
ics. *Optics Express* **17** (18), 15670–15678 1522
(2009) . 1523
- [60] Winship, I. R., Plaa, N. & Murphy, T. H. 1524
Rapid astrocyte calcium signals correlate 1525
with neuronal activity and onset of the hemo- 1526
dynamic response in vivo. *Journal of Neuro-* 1527
science **27** (23), 6268–6272 (2007) . 1528
- [61] Pasti, L., Volterra, A., Pozzan, T. & 1529
Carmignoto, G. Intracellular calcium oscil- 1530
lations in astrocytes: a highly plastic, bidi- 1531
rectional form of communication between 1532
neurons and astrocytes in situ. *Journal of* 1533
Neuroscience **17** (20), 7817–7830 (1997) . 1534

- 1498 [62] Poskanzer, K. E. & Yuste, R. Astrocytes
1499 regulate cortical state switching in vivo. *Pro-*
1500 *ceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*
1501 **113** (19), E2675–E2684 (2016) .
- 1502 [63] Mehina, E. M., Murphy-Royal, C. & Gordon,
1503 G. R. Steady-state free ca²⁺ in astrocytes is
1504 decreased by experience and impacts arteriole
1505 tone. *Journal of Neuroscience* **37** (34), 8150–
1506 8165 (2017) .
- 1507 [64] Shmuel, A., Augath, M., Oeltermann, A. &
1508 Logothetis, N. K. Negative functional mri
1509 response correlates with decreases in neu-
1510 ronal activity in monkey visual area v1.
1511 *Nature Neuroscience* **9** (4), 569–577 (2006) .
- 1512 [65] Moran, R. J., Pinotsis, D. A. & Friston,
1513 K. J. Neural masses and fields in dynamic
1514 causal modeling. *Frontiers in Computational*
1515 *Neuroscience* **7**, 57 (2013) .
- 1516 [66] Institoris, A. *et al.* Astrocytes amplify neu-
1517 rovascular coupling to sustained activation of
1518 neocortex in awake mice. *Nature Communi-*
1519 *cations* **13** (1), 7872 (2022) .
- 1520 [67] Havlicek, M. *et al.* Physiologically informed
1521 dynamic causal modeling of fmri data. *Neu-*
1522 *roimage* **122**, 355–372 (2015) .
- 1523 [68] Tesler, F., Tort-Colet, N., Depannemaecker,
1524 D., Carlu, M. & Destexhe, A. Mean-field
1525 based framework for forward modeling of lfp
1526 and meg signals. *Frontiers in Computational*
1527 *Neuroscience* **16** (2022). [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2022.968278)
1528 [3389/fncom.2022.968278](https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2022.968278) .
- 1529 [69] Ritter, P., Schirner, M., McIntosh, A. R. &
1530 Jirsa, V. K. The virtual brain integrates com-
1531 putational modeling and multimodal neu-
1532 roimaging. *Brain Connectivity* **3** (2), 121–145
1533 (2013) .
- 1534 [70] Kisler, K., Nelson, A. R., Montagne, A.
1535 & Zlokovic, B. V. Cerebral blood flow
1536 regulation and neurovascular dysfunction in
1537 alzheimer disease. *Nature Reviews Neuro-*
1538 *science* **18** (7), 419 (2017) .
- 1539 [71] Habib, N. *et al.* Disease-associated astro-
1540 cytes in alzheimer’s disease and aging. *Nature*
Neuroscience **23** (6), 701–706 (2020) . 1541
- [72] Booth, H. D., Hirst, W. D. & Wade-Martins, 1542
R. The role of astrocyte dysfunction in 1543
parkinson’s disease pathogenesis. *Trends in* 1544
Neurosciences **40** (6), 358–370 (2017) . 1545
- [73] Gui, Y.-X. *et al.* Four novel rare mutations of 1546
pla2g6 in chinese population with parkinson’s 1547
disease. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders* 1548
19 (1), 21–26 (2013) . 1549
- [74] Strokin, M., Seburn, K. L., Cox, G. A., 1550
Martens, K. A. & Reiser, G. Severe dis- 1551
turbance in the ca²⁺ signaling in astrocytes 1552
from mouse models of human infantile neu- 1553
roaxonal dystrophy with mutated pla2g6. 1554
Human Molecular Genetics **21** (12), 2807– 1555
2814 (2012) . 1556